

Effect of LAB173711 on leaf water potential of IR36 seedlings whose roots were kept at 11 °C in the greenhouse. IRRI, 1989.

was measured using a Scholander Pressure Bomb.

Leaf water potential (ψ_w) decreased significantly during chilling (-2.0 MPa in control). The decrease was minimized by the application of LAB173711 (-1.7 MPa) (see figure). The decrease was also lower in seedlings treated with LAB173711 and tetcyclacis (-1.6 MPa). Plants in the LAB173711 and LAB173711 + tetcyclacis treatments exhibited less yellowing than control plants.

The new synthetic ABA analog could be an effective tool in maintaining plant water status. □

A new phytohormone analog for preventing rice membrane injury after chilling

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We studied the effect on rice membrane stability of new abscisic acid (ABA) analog LAB173711 in combination with growth retardant tetcyclacis. Aqueous solutions of ABA, LAB173711, and LAB173711 + tetcyclacis (BASF, FRG), each at 10^{-4}

mol/liter, were sprayed on IR36 seedlings. After 24 h at 25 °C, the plants were transferred to 5 °C and kept for 3 d, then returned to 25 °C.

The second youngest leaf was cut off and immersed in 50 ml deionized distilled water, infiltrated under vacuum, and shaken for 1 h at room temperature. Electrolyte leakage was measured using a Cole-Parmer conductivity meter.

Membranes were injured in plants chilled for 3 d at 5 °C (see figure). Electrolyte leakage in plants sprayed with any of the three treatments was significantly lower. ABA decreased the leakage 9.18-fold; ABA analog LAB173711 alone, 6.35-fold.

LAB173711 + tetcyclacis was more effective; it decreased leakage 10.73-fold. □

Effect of LAB 173711 on electrolyte leakage from leaves of IR36 seedlings chilled at 5°C for 3 d. IRRI, 1989.

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Root cation exchange capacity (CEC) and yield-contributing parameters in rice in normal and alkali soils

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Alkali soils are reported to suffer from Ca deficiency and varieties with high root CEC are able to absorb relatively more cations. A relationship is reported to exist between root CEC and N uptake, and tolerance for soil alkalinity.

We studied the performance of eight rice varieties in normal soil (pH 7.8) and alkali soil (pH 9.5) in a pot experiment. NPK fertilizers were applied at 120, 26, and 49 ppm.

CEC of roots, air dry weight of roots, and length of roots were determined at active tillering 30 d after transplanting. Whole roots were thoroughly mixed and powdered to determine CEC. Plant height, fresh weight of shoot/plant, and grain test weight were recorded at harvest.

Table 1. Root characteristics in rice varieties grown in normal and alkali soils. Kanpur, India.

Variety	Root air-dry weight (g/pot)		Root length (cm)		Root CEC (meq/100 g)	
	Normal	Alkali	Normal	Alkali	Normal	Alkali
IR8	9.54	5.62	28	26	10.50	9.85
Jaya	8.31	4.07	30	27	9.75	8.25
M1-48	7.39	3.78	27	25	14.75	11.86
Pokkali	7.63	4.48	35	30	11.12	10.13
Pusa 2-21	5.2	4.47	32	28	12.75	7.90
Damodar	8.64	5.83	37	24	8.25	5.97
Saket 4	7.71	4.92	27	23	8.77	6.58
CSSR3	7.58	6.15	29	26	12.00	5.29
LSD (0.05)	0.42	0.38	3	2	1.82	1.35